

CREATOR WORKSHOP – The Power of Underutilized Leafy- Green Crops

Date: 15th -16th June 2023, Terceira Acores, Portugal

Hosted by: Biofontinhas “The Art of Balance” Unip. Lda.

RADIANT Project

The aim of this Workshop was to help showcase the added value of daily consumption of leafy greens to include the highly nutritious underutilized crops (Us). There also was an opportunity to see great examples of successful players and their contribution to the dissemination of the agroecological practices throughout the archipelago of the Azores. Practices that represent great respect with the soil food web that is crucial for soil health, farmer’s sustainability, and healthy consumers.

Contents

Background to BioFontinhas.....	3
Presenters' Biographies & Talk Titles	5
Organic UC Chef's Tasting Menu.....	9
Smoothie Making Workshop	11
BioFontinhas Field Trip.....	11
Organic Dairy Farm & Wine Museum	12
Appendix 1 - Programme (01/04/2023)	14

Background to BioFontinhas

BioFontinhas (*The Art of Balance*) delivers commercial scale organic horticultural production (under cover) of many different varieties and species of leafy- or micro-green vegetables and was founded by Avelino and Maria Ormonde. This production takes place in Fontinhas, Praia da Vitória, Terceira Island, Azores; which can be a very challenging environment in many ways, since Azores Island sits in the mid-Atlantic, which is often the location of hurricanes. Therefore, the production site – only two thousand square meters – is co-occupied by agroforestry and polytunnels, which house the vegetables; and so, presents production in a niche protected by natural- and build-barriers.

The production at BioFontinhas is pursued in a very systematic and organised manner, with seeds, and seedlings advanced to a developmental stage for sowing immediately after mature plants are harvested. Harvested beds are quickly prepared with only the addition of BioFontinhas own biologically active compost, compost tea and foliar spray made with native wild plants and other organic coproducts (waste (plant residue) material from around the farm; and augmented with manure from only one pig, sixteen chickens and one duck. This material is spread on top of the beds that are 'forked' to ensure adequate aeration (and 'top down fertilisation'). There is no use of pesticides or man-made products, plus all the agricultural work is carried out manually.

While there are many different product types spanning from leaves, roots, aromatics, and edible flowers; the bulk of the production centres on leafy- and micro-greens for use in restaurants, to sauté at home, and for "green smoothies" which is advocated by Avelino as a morning 'nutraceutical' for good health, and specifically to alleviate his joint pain. Some of the cultivars

grown here have been gathered from across the globe; and in this BioFontinhas produces the seed of the varieties they market too. So, seed storage, protection, and multiplication must also be factored into the commercial cycle too.

Historically, BioFontinhas products were not exported, and sold only to the Island's restaurants and households via the local organic market "Bioazorica". Commercially, the income of the farm is augmented by conferences, lectures, seminars, and workshops; also, research project involvements.

For more information on BioFontinhas, see this RADIANT Project [video](#). Also, an article using Life Cycle Assessment of the impact of leafy vegetable production by BioFontinhas has also been prepared, pending publication after science-peer review. To find out more about this, contact the lead authors: Dr Sophie Saget (sagets@tcd.ie).

Presenters' Biographies & Talk Titles

A series of presentations given at the beginning of the event are summarised below. Presentations can also be found [here](#).

Role of the Cuarentagri and Pervemac2 projects in promoting an sustainable agriculture in Azores Islands

David João Horta Lopes, University of Azores

David is an associate Professor in Plant Science at the Faculty of Agricultural Sciences and Environment of the University of the Azores. He has a Master in Integrated Pest Management, and PhD in Agricultural Sciences, and is an expert in crop protection. He has coordinated several international projects in the INTERREG II_B and MAC initiative, for example the INTERFRUTA, BIOMUSA, CABMEDMAC, CUARENTAGRI, PERVEMCAC2, as well as some National projects. He is also coordinator of several working groups, author of numerous scientific articles and technical books and supervisor of several PhD and Master thesis.

The Cuarentagri Project focuses on the identification of quarantine and regulated non-quarantine pests due to plant imports as well as movements of people between the study regions. This is to enable an out-risk analysis and establish contingency plans with mitigation measures to protect agricultural production across the Azores. Similarly, the Pervemac II project aims to encourage food security through improved food safety and reduced environmental contamination via more responsible agriculture in Macaronesia (the four main archipelagos of the Azores).

Miguel Garcia – Bioazorica (Organic Farmers COOP)

From the island of Pico, Miguel was part of institutions linked to sports, the social area, the church, music, local government, and the environment. In the latter, it is worth highlighting his integration in GEADA - Grupo de Alpinismo e Defesa do Ambiente from the very beginning, through which he participated in the exploration, discovery and topography of various volcanic cavities and capture of endemic cave fauna to scientific purposes. His profession as a social worker brought him to Terceira, where he lives with his family and works in the support team for risk groups in partnership with the Confederação Operária Terceirense and the Instituto de Ação Social dos Açores. He has been part of the Board of Directors of Cooperativa Bio Azórica for over 10 years, being its President for about 3 years. He is also an entrepreneur with businesses in the tourism and health sectors.

Trybio, the Association of Organic Farming Producers and Consumers.

Ana Branco – TRYBIO (Organic Farmers Association)

Ana has a master's degree in veterinary medicine from the ICBAS-University of Porto, carrying out her thesis on the theme of bovine culture in organic farming. She then undertook a post-graduate course in Organic Farming - Escola Superior Agrária de Ponte de Lima – Polytechnique Institute of Viana do Castelo. Since its formation in 2009, she participated in several organic farming events at regional, national, and international level. Passionate and motivated by this cause, since she returns to the Azores in 2011, she has been part of the associative movement, and participates in the organization of various events to promote and disseminate organic farming, together with a pioneering group of producers. She is part of the group of founding partners of TRYBIO and has

been the president of the association since its formation. She participated in several training courses, lectures, congresses, and workshops in the field of organic farming, either as an organizer, trainer, speaker, or participant. Also at a professional level, she has developed several actions to promote organic farming, namely in pedagogy and support for certification in organic farming.

Organic Agriculture, as a Solidarity Economy Initiative in the Promotion of Sustainability

Raquel Vargas – BioKairós Cooperative (São Miguel)

Raquel is the director at the insertion company - Biokairós (simultaneously a laboratory for the promotion of organic farming and an agricultural experience as a solidarity economy initiative for the professional integration of people at risk of social exclusion) of Kairós, a Cooperative of Incubation of Solidarity Economy initiatives. She has a degree in biology (teaching) and Master of Science in Special Education - Motor cognitive domain, with practical experience in the areas of social intervention, agri-environment and education. This initiative combines experimentation, training, and dissemination of organic farming, as an activity that contributes decisively to environmental preservation, ecologically appropriate and healthy. Raquel also performed the duties of:

- a teacher of basic and secondary education (public education);
- a coordinator of an alternative training space for young people in situations of social exclusion;
- a coordinator of the home for the empowerment of institutionalized young people;
- a technical coordinator insertion company – Cozinha Kairós, combining team and production management with the integration of people in situations of social exclusion; and,

- a coordinator for the implementation of insertion companies: Bikecenter, Pronto a Comer-Paim and Biokairós.

Other presentations included:

- **Mirica Organic Permaculture project**

Julian Floro (Faial)

- **Backyard Agroforestry project**

Eduardino Freitas (Faial)

- **The advantage of using Underutilized Crops in human diet**

Filomena Trindade (Functional Medicine)

Organic UC Chef's Tasting Menu

The unique UC-based day-1 lunch menu was created by the expert chefs. This integrated UCs grown by Biofontinhas with other locally produced and harvested foods.

Almoço CREATOR WORKSHOP

Ementa / Lunch Menu

Couvert A
 Taco de inhame , com bicuda, pimentos e pickle doce
 Yam taco with barramundi, peppers and sweet pickles

Entrada / Entree B
 Cremoso de favas com Ceviche de legumes, erva estrela e shot de favas
 Fava bean veloute whit vegetable ceviche, chikweed and fava shot

Peixe / Fish C
 Veja com infusão de levístico, creme de agrião do Líbano, perrexil e nastúrcio
 Mediterranean Parrotfish with lovage infusion, Lebanese cress cream, parsley and nasturtium

Carne / Meat D
 Vazia Grelhada, coração de bananeira, frutos secos e dedos do mar
 Grilled Sirloin, banana heart, dried fruits and sea fingers

Pré sobremesa / Pré desert E
 Sorvet de cardamomo, gel de planta do gelo, lima e maçã verde
 Cardamom Sordet, Livingstone daisy gel, lime and green apple

Sobremesa / Desert F
 Sweet Panc Dream (ruibarbo, limão, nêveda borragem, framboesa)
 Sweet UFC's Dream (rhubarb, lemon, calamint, borage and raspberry)

/inhos Tinto e Branco / Red and White Wines ANETO DOURO

Escola Profissional da Praia da Vitória

15 de junho de 2023

Avelino (far left) introducing and thanking the chefs for their amazing UC dishes, these were (left to right): Chef Diana Gravito (Restaurante Oficina, Shipyard Hotel); Chef Raúl Sousa (Professional School Teacher) and Chef Paulo Lourenço (Restaurante QB).

Smoothie Making Workshop

Avelino led the smoothie making workshop making workshop where leafy greens were blended to taste with locally grown sweet fruits (plus water); beverages were rich in phytochemicals and fibre. Avelino advocated a daily dose to help remedy joint pain.

BioFontinhas Field Trip

Different leafy green crops at varying stages of maturity cultivated organically under protective cover in raised beds. The only additions are an on-farm home-made compost.

Avelino was then recorded for the [video](#) produced by RADIANT partner FAO (Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations).

Organic Dairy Farm & Wine Museum

Participants took part in a field trip to Casa Agricola Soares, an organic dairy farm owned and managed by Antonio Soares (left: wearing the green t-shirt); whose cattle are raised extensively. Most of their organic milk is now exported to mainland Portugal, and dairy production in the Azores accounts for around 30% of Portuguese dairy consumption (c.f., [Efficiency of the Dairy Farms: A Study from Azores](#)

[\(Portugal\) \(sciendo.com\)\)](#)

At the [Museum of Wine](#), partners engaged with the museum owner Luís Brum, aided by RADIANT Coordinator (Prof. Marta Vasconcelos; right), and Avelino Ormonde (left).

At the museum, attendees also learned about heritage grape varieties, many of which can be cultivated locally according to non-intensive methods. Here production 'cells' (small 'fields') are

contained within volcanic rock walls. And the soil was also covered with volcanic rocks. Here, the walls protect from inclement weather, and the vines stand unsupported and so lay relatively close to the ground (below wall height). The dark rocks also absorb heat well and help create a microclimate within which the vines can grow well. Each vine is cultivated individually having been sown into soil 'pockets', where the rocks have been moved aside. Historically, each vine was intercropped, first with lupins which were mulched into the soil at late maturity (early flowering; as a green manure); and the pocket immediately re-sown with potato. Each vine-containing 'pocket' therefore produced grapes and staple food.

Appendix 1 - Programme (01/04/2023)

Day 1 – Workshop (Praia da Vitoria)

08:30 Coffee & Breakfast

09:00 Introduction - to the RADIANT Project, **The Power of Underutilized Crops "Leafy Greens"**.

- Marta Vasconcelos – Introduction to RADIANT project
- Pete Iannetta – Introduction to the CREATOR workshop

09:30 Presentations - including researchers, organic coops & associations, organic farmers, and functional medicine.

- D´Horta Lopes – Crop protection (Local University)
- Miguel Garcia – Bioazorica (Organic Farmers COOP)
- Ana Branco – TRYBIO (Organic Farmers Association)
- Raquel Vargas (São Miguel) – (BioKairos COOP)

10.30 - 1045 Coffee break

- Julian Floro (Faial) – Mirica Organic Permaculture Project
- Eduardino Freitas (Faial) – Backyard Agroforestry project
- Filomena Trindade (Functional Medicine) – The advantage of using Underutilized Crops in human diet

12:30 - Lunch & showcases by chefs

- **FOCUS** on local **UC´s** role on the food chain (Part 1)
 - Chef Raúl Sousa (Professional School Teacher)
 - Chef Paulo Lourenço (Restaurante QB)
 - Chef Diana Gravito (Restaurante Oficina)

14:45 Coffee break

15:00 – Showcases - Taste & UC´s role on the food chain (Part 2)

- Green Smoothie workshop (Avelino Ormonde)

16:30 – 17:30 Workshop Activity and Discussion: factors supporting the cultivation and consumption of underutilized crops.

19:00 Dinner at the Restaurant "O Pescador" (Praia da Vitoria)

<https://goo.gl/maps/Mhmab5PR2Gjq1QMfA>

Day 2 - Field Trial Visits

08:45 Bus Pick up at each hotel

09:00 Visit to Biofontinhas "The Art of Balance" (Avelino Ormonde)

10:30 Visit to organic dairy farm (Antonio Soares)

12:00 Biscoitos locality; visit the wine museum and ocean natural lava rock swimming holes.

<https://goo.gl/maps/kb4Yp8GDD59ZpCKu5>

12:30 Lunch at Caneta Restaurant. Family-owned project; angus beef mostly grass feed cattle to serve at the traditional restaurant.

<https://goo.gl/maps/sUwPfNjoDPf6MqnV8>

14:30 Visit the Algar do Carvão Cave

<https://goo.gl/maps/MRufnrUKqinJFMf5A>

16:00 Visit Quinta dos Acores. Family-owned project, produces; dairy products such as yogurt, cheese, ice cream and diverse processed meat products.

<https://goo.gl/maps/6KcwPWprG9GxZfbf7>

17:00 – 17:30 Hotel and/or Airport drop-off.